

THE PROCESS OF IMPROVING EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS FOR TEACHING ORTHOEPIA IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the current state of teaching orthography in higher education. Factors hindering the development of literary pronunciation are also analyzed. Methodical recommendations for teaching difficult-to-pronounce sounds are given. The important features of exercises and tasks in the development of literary pronunciation are highlighted on the basis of evidence.*

Keywords: *phonetics, orthography, dialect, exercise, assignment, speech technique, articulation, diction.*

It is important to suggest that all units specific to our language have been fully studied from the point of view of nationality. In particular, the sound system of Uzbek language has not yet been scientifically and methodically studied. Definitely, it is natural that the languages of peoples whose way of life and customs differ from each other have their own characteristics. Indeed, the orthography of Uzbek language has been scientifically studied in a certain sense, but the theoretical data collected to date in this regard cannot fully explain its uniqueness and national characteristics. In our native language, measured on the basis of other language samples since the 40s of 20th century due to the need of the time, there are still places, where we have not been able to completely get rid of the complexity of old samples. The result of this has a negative impact on education in the native language, especially on the teaching of the native language in schools. The content and main directions of the programs on the native and Uzbek languages in the republic were formed in the mid-1950s and have been updated with some changes. On this basis, textbooks were created that have repeatedly stood the test of time. On the one hand, it seems that the work in this direction has been improved and perfected. However, over the past quarter of a century, radical political, economic, spiritual and educational changes have taken place in our social life; there have been updates in our national worldview, in relation to the issue of personal education; the ideology of independence made new demands on each member of society, each industry, each aspect. Great changes have taken place and are taking place in our society. In the course of such changes, updates related to Uzbek linguistics and its development are also clearly visible.

Certainly, in Uzbek linguistics, the direction of substantive linguistics was formed, developed and achieved great success, studying language as universality, essence, possibility and causal system, and speech as individuality, event, reality and consequence. Orthopedics is a science that determines pronunciation norms, their justification and consolidation in the language. The subject and tasks of this science are the correct pronunciation of sounds and stresses in words. It is unusual to pronounce sounds that must always be present according to the pronunciation norms of words in Uzbek language (for example, speech, law) or change the meanings of the same words so that they do not change: olma, kiyma (noun) - olma, kiyma (verb). In addition, some letters have several pronunciation options, for example, boldi (Azamat

had only 20 minutes in class today) – boldi (Maftuna divided the bread in half). The above words are accepted and taught as homonyms in the educational process, but do not pay attention to the fact that there are two sounds represented by the same grapheme. However, despite the presence of options, some of them are preferred, and others are acceptable. Therefore, in order to speak Uzbek correctly, it is necessary to know and use orthoepic norms. The rules of spelling, incorrect pronunciation of sounds and stress in words seem not to cause any errors, but in fact, violation of pronunciation norms affects the culture of speech, spelling and the level of communication.

Besides that, mistakes and deviations from orthoepic norms distract the interlocutor, which makes him focus on incorrect pronunciation and not on the meaning of pronunciation. All this complicates understanding and communication. From this point of view, the teacher will be able to achieve his goal and attract the attention of students only if the oral speech used in the lesson is expressed clearly and correctly.

The difference in the pronunciation of words is not always associated with a person's lack of knowledge about this. People speaking Uzbek in all corners of the country speak Uzbek differently. They express their thoughts in local dialects. The saddest thing is that school teachers teach in their native language.

The reasons for this can be explained as follows:

Firstly, the teacher is influenced by the pronunciation of the area, where he lives.

Secondly, the teacher does not have the skills of literary pronunciation.

Thirdly, the teacher finds it convenient to teach in a dialect.

This has become the standard of Uzbek literary pronunciation, an indicator of the culture of speech. However, in addition to the difference between dialects, pronunciation is also affected by the environment in which people communicate and the level of education. For example, in everyday informal communication, all words and sounds are shortened, but words that according to the rules of spelling should not be pronounced, but used only in writing. Also, the unjustified use of foreign words, unclear diction - all this distances our speech from the orthoepic norms of our native language.

It is known that literary spelling rules are divided into two parts: the rules for pronouncing vowels and consonants and the rules for pronouncing stress. The following features are characteristic of orthoepic norms: variability, stability, universality, and consistency with the rules of the language. Philologists are engaged in the formation of orthoepic rules and norms. Before making any changes to the pronunciation of a particular word, scientists analyze the extent to which this variant is widespread, the historical and cultural connection with the vocabulary of past years, and its compliance with the rules and laws of the language.

However, literary language is used by educated people who know the rules of Uzbek pronunciation. The book style is distinguished by the clear pronunciation of all sounds and lines. It is often used for speeches in scientific circles. The colloquial style is characterized by the use of phrases suitable for communication in an informal setting. Many people use it in order to facilitate the process of mastering the literary language, the pronunciation norms of the spelling sections are divided into several sections:

- 1) pronunciation of vowels;
- 2) pronunciation of consonants;
- 3) pronunciation of special grammatical forms;
- 4) pronunciation of borrowed words;

5) pronunciation of stressed syllables.

Moreover, pronunciation norms depend on the real phonetic laws of Uzbek language, so phonetics and spelling are inseparable. In order to know all the laws of phonetics, understand stress, change stress when changing the form of a word, you need to have certain knowledge in this area.

Both disciplines study the sounds of speech. The similarity between phonetics and orthoepy is that the former allows for variations in the pronunciation of sounds, while orthoepy is a science that determines the correct version of such pronunciation according to the norms. In Uzbek language it is usually ignored. Correct literary pronunciation, knowledge of orthoepic norms and their use are indicators of a culturally literate person. The ability to speak one's native language correctly is necessary not only for eloquence, successful work, personal life, but also to be a worthy representative of one's people and an heir to the rich Uzbek culture. Literary pronunciation standards are both a stable and developing phenomenon, affecting both the past and the future of the language. This means that at any given moment these norms contain something that connects pronunciation at present time with the pronunciation characteristic of past periods of the literary language's development, and this is the result of internal laws of the development of the language system in the native language. The language appears as something new in pronunciation under the influence of the living oral practice of speakers.

It is known to everyone ep̄e norms, including orthoepic ones, help the literary language to preserve its integrity and universal recognition. They protect the literary language from dialect speech, social and professional slang, and the course of conversation. It allows the literary language to perform its main function - the cultural function. The literary norm depends on the conditions of speech, it limits the possibilities of use. Language means that are appropriate in one situation (everyday communication) may turn out to be absurd in another (official business communication). Historical changes in the norms of the literary language are a natural, objective phenomenon. It does not depend on the will and desire of individual native speakers. The development of society, changes in social conditions of life, the emergence of new traditions, the improvement of relations between people, the creativity of literature and art constantly revise the norms of pronunciation. The orthoepic norm is the most variable and dynamic. Native speakers need to be sensitive to its changes, correct their speech in time so that it is good.

Additionally, literary pronunciation is characterized by a certain unit, a norm, which is, in principle, obligatory for native speakers of a given language. Orthoepic norms are historically established and socially accepted rules for pronouncing words and grammatical forms of words. Orthoepic norms are nothing more than norms for forming grammatical forms of words and sentences or spelling norms of the literary language.

There are many specific spelling rules, but they can be divided into several groups:

- a) in the area of pronunciation of vowel sounds;
- b) norms for pronouncing consonants and their combinations;
- d) norms for pronouncing individual grammatical forms;
- e) features of pronunciation of borrowed words.

Particularly, pronunciation rules (norms) in Uzbek literary language in certain phonetic positions, as part of certain combinations of sounds, in different grammatical forms, phonetic word and rhythmic structure (correct formation of stress) can separately relate to the pronunciation of sounds. Thus, for the convenience of the user, the basic orthoepic rules of

Uzbek language include the pronunciation of vowel sounds (in different situations in a word, as well as when determining the place of stress) and the pronunciation of consonants (as well as in different situations in a word), combinations of consonants, combinations with some vowel sounds, different vowels can be divided into defining ones.

The tendency in the field of orthography is a process that constantly intensifies or disappears depending on the changing level of intensity of phonetic acquisition of words of a foreign language. A foreign language always strives to subordinate its spelling, orthographic and grammatical rules and laws. It is believed that the degree of "subordination" of the study of a foreign language to linguistic norms depends on its "assimilation" with this language.

Certainly, vowel norms can, for one reason or another, begin to "relax" fluctuations in pronunciation norms and appear if they are public in nature, the emergence of variants of literary norms lead to the emergence and strengthening of a new pronunciation norm. Along with mandatory pronunciation norms, orthoepy is, first of all, a situation when the old (historical) pronunciation variant is still actively used along with the new variant in the language at a given time.

Pronunciation norms of Uzbek language have developed historically. Of course, it was a long process. Modern Uzbek literary pronunciation is based on the Karluk dialect. Modern pronunciation norms gradually formed on the basis of the collision of pronunciation variants in different regional dialects, different social groups and partly in different styles. From a chronological point of view, the difference in pronunciation variants can be assessed as "small" and "large" standards. Here we see the following situation: a new pronunciation replaces the old one, but perhaps both pronunciations coexist in parallel for a long time. For example, machit - mosque, kabutar - dove. Failure to comply with uniform pronunciation rules (orthoepic norms) can lead to serious difficulties in the future. Traditionally, knowledge of orthoepic rules is considered an indicator of a sufficiently high cultural level of a person. In addition, the unity of pronunciation norms is supported by spelling rules, otherwise they have a negative impact on each other, which ensures inadequate understanding of the written text. Literary pronunciation skills are not found among the requirements for a teacher of the native language in scientific and methodological sources.

It is clear that teaching literary pronunciation in higher educational institutions is carried out mainly on the basis of textbooks and teaching aids, as well as Internet information. Language teaching in higher pedagogical education is carried out on the basis of educational tasks. In this regard, there is a lack of teaching materials on literary pronunciation in the content of textbooks. In order to come to unambiguous conclusions, it is necessary to analyze higher school textbooks from the point of view of orthoepic education.

By summarizing it should be suggested that the actual issue of literary pronunciation, and all school teachers, especially the teacher of the subject of native language, should have the opportunity to be an example for their students in this regard. In this case, the expected result is achieved only when conducting pronunciations individually with each student of the group in the educational department of spelling on the subject of native language or other subjects related to the field of higher education.

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